

Oslo, 13.11.2023

Dear Dr Olwenn Martin,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of the manuscript "Protocol: Testing the performance of INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies". We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback and are grateful for the comments suggestions for improvement of our manuscript.

We have responded to each comment individually, and the suggested revisions are shown with blue text in the tables below. Tables 1 and 2 contain an overview of our point-by-point response to all comments and the revisions provided (with line numbers for the revised text in the clean version of the revised manuscript).

We look forward to hearing from you regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Table 1. Response to the comments in the editorial triage report.

Comment Editorial triage of stage one submission	Author response
<p>3. Plan for the analysis of data and reporting of results A detailed plan for data analysis and reporting is given. It does not appear to include analyses of the influence of the characteristics of selected participants on study outcomes. This is related to minor issue highlighted in transparency domain</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out that this needs clarification. The study has not been powered to analyse if participant characteristics impact the outcome. In addition to the text “<i>Data on participant expertise will be collected (see Supplementary materials 3) and used to see if there are correlations between the level of consistency and the level and type of expertise. However, statistical analyses addressing such effects will not be performed as we are not able to power the study for such analyses</i>” (Lines -), we have included the following text for clarification:</p> <p>(Lines 495-498) “The study is not powered to allow meaningful analysis of impact of participant characteristics on the results. It was considered not possible to power the study for such analyses because the number of participants needed would be higher than can be achieved with the resources available to the research team.”</p>
<p>4. Transparency and reproducibility Methods are described in detail. The only issue with transparency identified at this stage is related to the identification of study participants to be invited and whether this may introduce bias.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out.</p> <p>Participants will be recruited through the networks of PG and SAG members, covering a wide range of institutions/persons affiliated with different institutions. This was considered to be an appropriate way of recruiting because i) it is less time-consuming, ii) because the PG and SAG in total have large networks involved in relevant work which will make it easier to reach out to persons fulfilling the criteria for inclusion, and iii) the chance of positive answers may be increased. We expect that spreading the information through networks so that people receive the invitation from someone they know may increase the possibility for acceptance of invitations.</p>

	<p>However, such an approach has limitations, and the following text has been included to specify this:</p> <p><i>(Lines 491-494)</i> “By recruiting from the network of PG and SAG members, we attempt to involve a broad and diverse group of experts from different institutions in the user testing, while working within the resources that the research team has available. However, the final group of participants may not be representative of all potential users of the tool.”</p>
<p>5. Ethics and interests</p> <p>The informativeness of the declarations of interests for all co-authors available as supplementary information is very variable. This should be addressed.</p> <p>Ethical approval has been obtained, no reference number has been provided.</p>	<p>The declarations of interest for the co-authors were completed according to the guidance in the “Notes”-section in the form. The variations in the level of information are the result of different interpretation of what the level of detail should be. To make the level of information more similar, more detailed guidance is needed to reduce the possibility for different interpretation. We therefore hope that you can accept the variation in informativeness of these declarations.</p> <p>With regard to the ethical approval, the text was imprecise and has been revised as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 171-173 and 554-556)</i> “Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian Institute of Public Health on February 7th, 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.”</p>

Table 2. Response to the referee comments.

Structured assessment	Comment number	Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Report, reviewer comments	Author response
<p>2. Are the proposed hypotheses logical, rational, and/or plausible?</p>	<p>1.</p>	<p>Reviewer 2, Comment 1.</p> <p>As reviewer knowing nothing about INVITES-IN (as not released to the public yet) but commenting on a protocol for its performance testing is per se a bit odd. But the study design appears to be well-structured and very detailed, with clear objectives and how they will be evaluated. The statistical part is in parts a bit unclear, but I guess of secondary importance as the exact number of minimal sample sizes should be considered only as guidance.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out that this needs clarification. We agree and have specified that detailed description of the creation of INVITES-IN is available in the published protocol. The revised text is as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 69-71)</i> “We are developing a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies called INVITES-IN (detailed description of the creation of this tool is available in the protocol by Svendsen et al. (2023)).”</p> <p>We agree that the statistical part is very detailed. This is because we consider it important to present how the data we are collecting will be analysed to ensure that we collect all the data we need and to avoid bias in the choice of method for data analysis which could be introduced if the analysis were not planned in detailed before the data were collected. In addition, this is in accordance with the principles of transparency. We would therefore like to keep the level of details. However, to make the text describing the analyses of the assessment of consistency (Section 2.3.1) easier to follow, the detailed description of the statistical methods for</p>

			assessing consistency has been included in two subsections (2.3.1.1 Detailed description of the statistical methods, and 2.3.1.2 Sample size estimation).
2.	<p>Reviewer 2, Comment 2.</p> <p>The manuscript states “<i>expected end users of INVITES-IN are persons preparing literature reviews including in vitro studies ...</i>”, but the main users of <i>in vitro</i> data outcomes (especially related to simple KIEs) are usually those involved in <i>in silico</i> work (QSAR, AOP, IATA, Read-Across etc.) in preparation for chemical hazard and risk assessments (and probably only those non-experimenters who really have to read the details). I am wondering how well these experts were included, as “<i>expected to have experience with in vitro methods</i>” is rather vague and could be misunderstood as “being involved in the lab and/or test system development”.</p>		<p>We agree, and the text has been revised as follows:</p> <p>(Lines 78-80) “This includes persons having practical experience from carrying out <i>in vitro</i> studies, and/or experience with evaluating evidence from <i>in vitro</i> studies.”</p>
3.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 1</p> <p>The manuscript does not clearly describe the signalling questions or the risk of bias (RoB) domains underlying this method, or how the signalling questions are rated to complete the RoB analysis. These steps should be clearly stated/defined either in the methods, or in the supplemental materials. Without this information,</p>		<p>Thank you for pointing out that this needs clarification. The tool is currently under development, and the creation of the tool includes three studies (described in the published protocol by Svendsen et al., 2023). It is not possible to describe the signalling questions or the rating of these questions before all three studies have been performed, because this is part of the process of creating</p>

		<p>the reader cannot discern the appropriateness of the tool or the robustness of the overall method. For example, it would be concerning if a quantitative scoring method was used to evaluate the signalling questions and assess RoB. In a recent consensus report entitled "<u>The Use of Systematic Review in EPA's Toxic Substances Control Act Risk Evaluations (2021)</u>" domain (see Table 3) the National Academy of Sciences (NAS) stated that: "The reliance on numeric quality scores is problematic because scores do not distinguish between high- and low-quality studies, and the relationship between quality scores and an association or effect is inconsistent and unpredictable"...and "More generally, the use of numerical scoring in critical appraisal does not follow standards for the conduct of systematic reviews."</p>	<p>the tool. However, we will follow the standards for the conduct of systematic reviews and will not use numeric scoring. We agree that the text needed clarification, and it has been revised as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 85-87) "The outcome of the three studies described in the protocol for the creation of INVITES-IN (Svendensen et al., 2023) will determine which bias domains and items that will be included in INVITES-IN."</i></p> <p>The approach chosen fulfils the framework for developing quality assessment tools (Whiting et al., 2017), which to our knowledge is the only existing framework for how to develop quality appraisal tools. We are performing three studies, all involving expert participation as described in the published protocol for the creation of INVITES-IN to ensure the appropriateness of the tool, to reduce the level of expert judgements made by the project group and also ensure that the tool development is based on a wide range of feedback from the experts that are the intended user of the tool.</p>
	<p>4.</p>	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 2</p> <p>The RoB domains should include a domain for financial conflict of interest. This recent publication suggests that the INVITES-IN tool does not</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment.</p> <p>The bias domains included in the tool that will be applied for the user testing, will be identified in the three studies performed to create the tool</p>

		<p>consider financial conflicts of interest as a RoB domain (see Table 3). While the RoB domains are not clearly listed in the current manuscript, it is critical that the authors consider financial conflict of interest as a key RoB domain, as recommended by the National Academy of Sciences, which states that “Funding sources should be considered in the risk-of-bias assessment conducted for systematic reviews that are part of an IRIS assessments.” (Ref: National Research Council. Review of EPA’s Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) Process. Page. 79. Washington, DC: National Academies Press; 2014).</p>	<p>(described in the published protocol by Svendsen et al., 2023), and it is therefore not possible to know which domains that will be included before all three studies are completed. In the first of the three studies performed to create INVITES-IN, an internal validity item bank containing all bias domains and issues discovered from the literature and focus group discussions will be created. In the second study, expert participants may suggest additionally bias domains and items. Thus, all domains included in the literature and additional domains considered relevant and important by the experts will be included in the beta version of INVITES-IN. This will then be used for the testing described in this protocol.</p>
	5.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 3</p> <p>The authors should consider an expanded and more robust definition of NAMs, as suggested by the NAS in a recent report.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment.</p> <p>The tool is not restricted to application on NAMs. INVITES-IN is created for in vitro studies and will be designed specifically for all cell culture studies, including NAMs, through the user testing. This is the reason for not going into detailed definitions of NAM, but rather to only include one example.</p>
	6.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 4</p>	<p>We agree, and this is now included in Table 2.</p>

		The authors should also consider expanding the participant affiliation criteria to include NGOs (section 2.2.2.1).	
Is the methodology and analysis pipeline sound (and, if appropriate, statistically powered)?	7.	<p>Reviewer 1, Comment 1</p> <p>The aim was to test of the performance of INVITES-IN. By performance, they mean the extent to which results of using INVITES-IN are the same for different users (consistency), the amount of time and cognitive effort it takes to apply INVITES-IN (assessor workload), the precision and potential for systematic error in results of applying INVITES-IN (accuracy), and how easy it is to use INVITES-IN (user experience).</p> <p>My comment is about the accuracy where details are missing in such protocols.</p> <p>I feel the authors should use checklist to consider important steps in methodology dealing with accuracy (e.g. <u>Stard</u>), especially with blinding/blindness that should be detailed, statistical analyses that should include AUO/DOR/ sensitivity, specificity, predictive values, and likelihood ratios by combining what is true and positive/ negative and confidence interval.</p>	<p>Thank you for these suggestions. In this study, we will address accuracy in the application of INVITES-IN in terms of the precision against the gold-standard, to find out to what degree the participant ratings are in line with the gold standard ratings.</p> <p>The statistical analyses have been chosen to evaluate how precisely INVITES-IN characterises internal validity and the potential for systematic differences. How precisely INVITES-IN characterises internal validity will be measured as the association between the ratings of participants and the gold-standard for the same signalling question for the same study, and also by the identification of learning effects (described in detail in Section 2.3.3.1). The potential for systematic differences will be described via histograms of the user-ratings for each level of the gold-standard ratings (Section 2.3.3.2). The outcome of these analyses will be used to identify needs for improvement of the guidance on how to rate the signalling questions, which is the reason for addressing</p>

		<p>This is important because the authors should clearly mention on (D) what extent the tool will be consider accurate enough (e.g. 80% for Sensitivity/ Specificity).</p> <p>I strongly not recommended statistical test based (p significant), since association with gold standard is different to be predict low bias if positive/negative.</p>	<p>accuracy in the user testing study. We do not consider it relevant to set a threshold for accuracy, because the purpose of the accuracy analyses is not to conclude whether the accuracy is sufficient or not, but rather to identify where users deviate from the gold-standard in their ratings to identify need for improvement of the guidance.</p> <p>The <u>Stard</u> checklist is designed for studies on diagnostic accuracy. In our opinion, the elements in this checklist that are relevant for the user testing of INVITES-IN is included in the protocol (e.g. the purpose of the study, the objectives, the eligibility criteria for participants, how we will recruit participants, which data we will collect, and how these data will be analysed and used to create the release version of INVITES-IN).</p>
	8.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 1</p> <p>The authors should explicitly define what a project group is</p>	<p>We agree, and have inserted the following:</p> <p>(Lines 129-130): “A project group (PG) has been established with the responsibility for drafting the protocol and performing the study.”</p>
	9.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 2</p> <p>For validation purposes, the authors should require participants in the user testing to disclose any</p>	<p>We agree, and the following is included in the Supplementary Materials 2:</p> <p>(Lines 734-740) “Do you have any financial interests (e.g. employment, shares, grants, or</p>

		financial conflicts of interest for any of the studies being evaluated (Section 2.2.2.1).	<p>other income) that could be affected by the findings of this study? [If no, answer "None". If yes, please describe the financial interests]</p> <p>Do you have any non-financial interests (e.g. publicly held positions, strong beliefs, or roles in which you are a formal representative of another organisation), that could be affected by the findings of this study? [If no, answer "None". If yes, please describe the non-financial interests”</p>
	10.	<p>Reviewer 3, Comment 3</p> <p>Under data analysis and reporting, the authors should also consider collecting information on participants' race/ethnicity.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment.</p> <p>Information on race and ethnicity are classified as sensitive information (at least in Norway) and the importance of obtaining such data should therefore always be considered before including questions on such information in a questionnaire. We cannot see that this information would be of great importance in this project and have therefore not included collection of information on the participants race/ethnicity.</p>
Are the methods detailed and clear	11.	Reviewer 1, Comment 1	Thank you for pointing out that this needs clarification.

<p>enough to permit replication of the experimental procedures and analysis pipeline?</p>		<p>Clarity of the systematized review (not systematic here in my opinion) and how will be used here might be clarified.</p>	<p>The practical exercise aims to emulate a real-world application of INVITES-IN by simulating the systematic review process, however, we are not aiming to perform a complete systematic review. To clarify this, the text has been revised:</p> <p>(Lines 233-236) “The practical exercise aims to emulate a real-world application of INVITES-IN by simulating the validity assessment step in the systematic review process. The validity assessment step includes critical appraisal of studies by pair of experts that first do the assessment individually and then harmonise the results.”</p>
	<p>12.</p>	<p>Reviewer 2, Comment 1</p> <p>What were the criteria for “scientists having good experience with <i>in vitro</i> methods”? Only experimenters? Some more details about the “experience space” would be welcome (besides the eligibility criteria in Table 2).</p>	<p>We agree that this needs clarification, and the revised text is as follows:</p> <p>(Lines 78-80) “This includes persons having practical experience from carrying out <i>in vitro</i> studies, and/or experience with evaluating evidence from <i>in vitro</i> studies.”</p>
	<p>13.</p>	<p>Reviewer 2, Comment 2</p> <p>Power simulations: “<i>The rating were therefore correct for 83.8% of the studies. This corresponded to an ICC of approximately 0.65</i>”. Please provide the mathematical equation. The whole description on page 16 is unclear as no formal mathematical</p>	<p>In section 2.3.1.1, we have now described how the 95% CIs for the ICC are obtained (model-based semi-parametric bootstrapping).</p> <p>In section 2.3.1.2, we have now removed the confusing description of the simulation, and instead A) included mathematical formulae for</p>

		description of the simulation and assessment is provided, e.g. the term “95% confidence interval” has not been specified (I guess the percentiles of the simulation outcome distribution are meant), and “95% margin of error for estimating ICC” is rather unclear in the context of simulations.	how to create the simulated data, and B) provided the R code for both the simulation and the sample size assessment.
	14.	Reviewer 2, Comment 3 I found it rather hard to follow the description for the power simulations (especially, which & how the random generator is used), and would suggest to provide the corresponding calculation code(s) as suppl. material. (assuming R was used?).	We have tried to rewrite the section, and in addition we have now provided the R code in the supplemental material.
Other comments	15.	Reviewer 1, Comment 1 I should mention that I am not familiar with such In vitro techniques, but I have some experience of epidemiology and clinical toxicology. However, sometimes it is hard to follow as I mentioned before.	We hope the revised text is improved and easier to follow.
	16.	Reviewer 1, Comment 2 Details of ICC and numbers of judges and attempt is over developed and should be mentioned in supplemental, with keeping the main attended methods and results	Thank you for pointing out this. To make the text describing the analyses of the assessment of consistency (Section 2.3.1) easier to follow, the detailed description of the statistical methods for assessing consistency has been included in two subsections (2.3.1.1 Detailed

			<p>description of the statistical methods, and 2.3.1.2 Sample size estimation).</p>
	17.	<p>Reviewer 1, Comment 3</p> <p>Potential limitations of such approaches should be discussed</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. We agree with this comment. Therefore, a new section with the heading “Limitations” has been included. The text is as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 490-501)</i> “Limitations</p> <p>By recruiting from the network of PG and SAG members, we attempt to involve a broad and diverse group of experts from different institutions in the user testing, while working within the resources that the research team has available. However, the final group of participants may not be representative of all potential users of the tool.”</p> <p>The study is not powered to allow meaningful analysis of impact of participant characteristics on the results. It was considered not possible to power the study for such analyses because the number of participants needed would be higher than can be achieved with the resources available to the research team.</p> <p>The study is not powered to allow analysis of impact of in vitro studies on the results. It was considered not possible to power the study for such analyses because the number of studies</p>

			that would need analysing is unrealistically high.”
	18.	Reviewer 1, Comment 4 An ethical approval was obtained by Norwegian Institute of Public Health: February 7 th , 2022, 22/04212	Thank you for pointing this out. The text was imprecise and has been revised as follows: (Lines 171-173 and 554-556) “Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian Institute of Public Health on February 7 th , 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.”